

TEACHERS AND PARENTS SUPPORT IN THE ADMINISTRATION OF SELF-PACED LEARNING MODULES IN MANAGING GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF KINDERGARTEN PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has a huge impact on teaching and learning in both schools and universities. The changes in learning modality in the education challenge the proponent to conduct the study if self-paced learning module is effective to be used by the kindergarten pupils. The study is focused on the teachers' and parents' support in the administration of self-paced learning modules in managing the growth and development of kindergarten pupils. This descriptive and correlational study utilized 38 kindergarten teachers and 75 kindergarten parents from 15 public schools in Candelaria East District and was conducted within the school year 2020-2021. The researcher-made survey questionnaire was used in this study, teachers answered through Google form, and parents were given printed survey questionnaires to gather the needed data. The study revealed that teacher's and parent's support in the administration of self-paced learning modules as perceived by the respondents has a positive significant relationship in terms of academic competency. It shows that the respondents are always supportive in guiding the child in their learning. There is a positive significant relationship between teachers and parent's support in the administration of self-paced learning modules and the growth and development of kindergarten pupils which implies that teachers and parents play a vital role in molding the child's development. The study suggests that the quality of self-paced learning modules should be appropriate to the level of maturity and sophistication of the learners which will help to develop the different skills of the child.

Keywords: Quality of SLMs, Teacher Support, Parent Support, Academic Competency, Aspects of Development